

CHALLENGING LESSONS FROM THE SECOND WORLD-WIDE FAILURE EXERCISE (WWFE-II): PREDICTING FAILURE IN POLYMER COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER 3-D STATES OF STRESS

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Abstract

In order to determine the accuracy of current theories for predicting failure in polymer composite laminates under three-dimensional (3-D) states of stress, the authors have organized an activity called the Second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II). This paper provides some of the lessons learnt from the second stage ('Part B') of WWFE-II. The level of maturity and accuracy of the leading 3-D failure theories for composites are assessed against experimental data and their strengths and weaknesses are identified. WWFE-II builds upon the process and philosophy developed during the First World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE) with the clear aims of ensuring that the assessment is objective, transparent and represents an effective, accessible benchmark for use by the composites community.

1. Introduction

Over the last 20 years, the authors of the paper and their colleagues have been leading international activities, known as the World-Wide Failure Exercises (WWFE), to assess the predictive capabilities of current failure theories and their limitations and boundaries of applicability. Three exercises have been co-ordinated and these are known as:

- The First World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE)[1], which dealt with in-plane failure criteria.
- The Second World-Wide Failure Exercise, (WWFE-II)[2][3], dealing with 3-D failure criteria.
- The Third World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III), addressing damage and continuum damage mechanics under in-plane stresses, with the presence of stress concentration and cracking

due to in-plane, bending and thermal loadings. The third exercise is described somewhere [4].

The first exercise was launched and coordinated between 1996-2004 to deal with benchmarking of failure criteria under two dimensional or in-plane (2D) loading situations. A total of 15 participating groups, who were the originators of 19 different methodologies, took part and their failure theories were compared with one another and compared against 14 sets of experimental data. The results, in the form of papers written by the originators of the theories, have been published in three special issues of an international journal and then assembled into a text book[1]. One of the high priority gaps, identified in first WWFE, was the need to examine the fidelity of failure theories when applied to three-dimensional (3-D) (i.e. triaxial) states of stress.

The Second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II) was organised by the authors of this paper with the objective of extending the assessment of predictive failure criteria from 2-D to 3-D states of stress, using the same philosophy of 'blind prediction' that was a central feature of the first WWFE. In order to accommodate the 'blind prediction' process whilst also allowing contributors with the opportunity to modify their theories and their predictions in the light of further experimental evidence being made available, the exercise was conducted in two parts, referred to as 'Part A' and 'Part B'.

Essentially, there is a huge interest, as well as an urgent need for an independent evaluation and benchmarking of the current failure criteria for designing fibre reinforced polymer composite laminates under three-dimensional (3-D) loadings.

Broadly, that has been driven by two complementary realities (a) industries seek quicker life cycles of introducing new conceptual and detailed designs of components and structures into service and (b) manufacturing methods have been improving to cope with the wide spread demands on making complex shapes and geometries. With this advancement in mind, thicker components are frequently encountered and, as a consequence, it is inevitable that 3-D stresses are created. What is certain is that design engineers seek to utilise reliable and well validated tools as a means of achieving 'right first-time' design of components under general 3-D stresses (i.e. triaxial stresses), without resorting to a lengthy and often unnecessary process of testing and experimentation. Unfortunately, a key question, which remains largely unanswered, is how well can the current tools and failure models predict 3-D failure in composites?.

In WWFE-II, 'Part A' ([5] to [19]) was conducted to capture full details of the theoretical models of selected leading failure criteria, which were developed and implemented by their originators. 'Part A' provided a platform for the participants to run their analyses and make blind predictions of a set of 12 Test Cases, which were chosen to challenge the models to their extremes. A total of 12 groups representing 12 failure criteria have participated, and their methods covered a wide range of failure models. A recent special issue of Journal of Composite Materials, [2], provided a detailed account of 'Part A'.

The organisers (Kaddour and Hinton) initiated 'Part B' of WWFE-II after the completion of 'Part A', by means of a letter and data pack issued to the participants, containing the following:

- Full instructions for participating in 'Part B' (including a defined format for their 'Part B' paper submission).
- Tables and figures of the experimental results for each of the test cases defined in 'Part A'.
- A description of the pedigree of the experimental results and of the material properties provided by the organisers.

The results for 'Part B' of the WWFE-II are contained in another special issue of Journal of Composite Materials, Ref[3]. The special issue contains the following:

- (a) An introduction, written by the organisers[19],
- (b) A paper giving full description, provided by the organisers, of the experimental results and their origins for each of the test cases employed in the exercise[21],
- (c) Individual papers ([22] to [33]) provided by the participants, describing the degree of correlation between their individual predictions and the experimental data, and a description of any refinements in theory introduced to resolve shortfalls and
- (d) A final paper, [34], provided by the organisers, which contains an assessment of the overall predictive capabilities of the various theories when compared with the experimental results.

The theories have been assessed and ranked according to their abilities to predict the experimental results for failure of a plastic polymer, unidirectional fibre reinforced lamina and multi-directional laminates under various 3-D states of stress. The assessment has been made to both the 'blind' predictions, submitted in 'Part A' prior to supplying experimental data, and the modified predictions, submitted in 'Part B', i.e. after the experimental data had been made available.

This paper brings to conclusion both 'Part A' and 'Part B' of the WWFE-II. It gives an account of a few selected lessons learnt, the gaps which need to be bridged, and how future research activities could be carried out to provide validated tools to the design community.

2. Description of Test Cases

The Test Cases analysed in the WWFE-II are listed in Table 1. These twelve Test Cases comprise an isotropic polymeric material, without reinforcing fibres, (Test Case 1), unidirectional laminae (Test Cases 2 to 7) and multi-directional laminates (Test Cases 8 to 12).

They are concerned with predicting nine 'tri-axial' failure envelopes (Test Cases 1-3, 5-8, 10-11) and three stress-strain curves (Test Cases 4, 9 and 12). The Test Cases in WWFE-II (described in Ref[2]) have been chosen carefully to stretch each theory to the full in order to shed light on their strengths and weaknesses. They are focused on a range of classical, continuous fibre, laminated, reinforced polymer composites subjected, in the absence of

stress concentrations, to a variety of triaxial loading conditions. The key issues being explored are:

- The means by which the theories distinguish (if at all) between the effects of anisotropy and heterogeneity.
- The types of failure mechanism employed and the way that each is implemented within any given theory.
- The accuracy and bounds of applicability of each theory.

Five types of fibres, covering glass and carbon fibres, and five types of matrices were used to make the five different unidirectional laminae (E-glass/MY750, S-glass/epoxy, T300/319, AS Carbon/epoxy and IM7/8551-7). Ref [6] provides a full listing of the input data describing the mechanical and the thermal properties of the 5 types of fibres, 5 matrices and 5 unidirectional laminae.

Details of the experimental results used in WWFE-II are fully described in Ref[21]. The test results were generated by various laboratories around the world, over a period of time.

3. Theoretical models used in WWFE-II

A total of 12 groups, see Table 2, representing 12 failure criteria, have participated, and their methods covered the following failure models:

- 3-D Maximum strain theory, referred to as Bogetti's model,[13][28].
- Micromechanical based Hybrid Mesoscopic (MHM) 3-D approach, referred to as Carrere's model, [10][25].
- Failure Mode Concept (FMC) model, referred to as Cuntze's model,[18][33].
- MicroMechanics of Failure (MMF) model, referred to as Tsai-Ha's model, [12][27].
- Multi-Continuum micro-mechanics Theory (MCT), referred to as Hansen's model, [14][29].
- Anisotropic plasticity, bridging model and constituents' generalised maximum stress, referred to as Huang's model, [8][23].
- Hashin's model, [17][32].
- 3-D physically-based constitutive model, referred to as Pinho's model, [7][22].
- Physically based 3-D phenomenological model, referred to as Puck's model, [15][30].
- Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory, referred to as Rotem's model, [9][24].

- Maximum strain energy method, referred to as Wolfe's model, [16][31].
- Christensen's theory, [11][26].

It is worth pointing out that the originators of 10 of the theories made their own contributions to the exercise. However, two of the theories; namely Hashin's and Christensen's theories, were not directly represented by their originators but by colleagues who were able to carry out a thorough examination of the models.

In 'Part B', the participants took the opportunity to make an adjustment and offered revised predictions for a number of the Test Cases. It was noted 11 of the 12 participants made various tuning and that Huang made a revision to all the 12 Test Cases. In this paper, a distinction will be drawn between predictions emanating from the 'Part A' submissions and those emanating from the 'Part B' submissions. The theories that were modified in 'Part B' are marked as 'Name-B', e. g. Carrere-B, Cuntze-B, Huang-B, etc...

4. Correlations between models and experiments

Only selected Test Cases are chosen here to illustrate some aspects of the correlation between the models and the associated experimental results. The selected cases are marked in Table (1) and these are Test Cases 1, 5 and 12. A full account of the correlation between the 12 Test Cases and the 12 models can be found in Kaddour and Hinton [34].

Test Case 1:

This Test Case is related to the behaviour of an isotropic polymer material under triaxial loading. The material was MY750 epoxy and the task is the prediction of failure envelope under the combined loading σ_x versus σ_z (with $\sigma_y = \sigma_z$). The stresses applied are such that those in y and z directions are equal while that in x direction varies proportional to that in y direction. A schematic of the loading configurations is illustrated in Figure 1. Also shown in the figure is a comparison between the failure envelopes predicted by different contributors and test results for this configuration. The envelopes are superimposed in order to observe the general differences and similarities between the various predictions. The ratio between the predicted and measured data at one of the stress ratios is depicted in the bar chart in figure as a function of the model

employed.

The results show that the majority of the models gave seemingly a good correlation with the available test data. However, some of the striking difference:

- All the models but one predicted an enhancement in the strength in the compression-compression stress space.
- 10 out of 12 of the models predicted open envelope under hydrostatic compression and one out of 12 under hydrostatic tension.
- The ratio between the predicted and measured data varied from 0.27 to 1.9.

Test Case 5:

Test Case 5 is concerned with prediction of the failure envelope of an E-glass/epoxy unidirectional lamina subjected to a set of triaxial stresses, given by a wide range of combined σ_2 and $\sigma_1 (= \sigma_3)$. Note that σ_1 is applied parallel to the fibre direction, σ_3 is applied in the through thickness direction and σ_2 is applied in the transverse direction (see Figure 5).

Figure 2 shows a comparison between the failure envelopes predicted by different contributors and test results for this configuration. The envelopes are superimposed in order to observe the general differences between the various predictions. The correlation ratio (CR) between the predicted and measured data at one of the stress ratios (SR) is depicted in the bar chart in figure as a function of the model employed. Some of the salient points about the results are:

- All the models predicted an enhancement in the strength in the compression-compression stress space.
- Four of the models predicted open envelope under hydrostatic compression. For those closed envelopes, the ratio (CR) between the highest and lowest theoretical prediction under hydrostatic pressure is more than 10.
- The ratio (CR) between the predicted and measured data varied from 0.15 to 2.7.

Comparison between Test Case 1 and 5:

The same models were employed to predict the failure of an isotropic un-reinforced polymer matrix material (Test Case 1) and an anisotropic, heterogeneous, E-glass/epoxy unidirectional lamina (Test Case 5) under triaxial stresses. The difference between the two cases is that Test Case 1 is for the

pure resin while Case 5 is for a unidirectional lamina with 60% fibre volume fraction, using the same matrix as that in Case 1. A quick glance at the results of Test Case 1 (Figure 1) and Test Case 5 (Figure 2) indicate that the majority of the models predicted an open envelope for the isotropic materials and closed envelope for the composite lamina. Although there are no test data to confirm the accuracy of this trend under hydrostatic pressure, the assumptions made by some of the models must be questionable.

Test Case 12:

The Test Case pertains to predicting the through-thickness compressive stress-strain curves ($\sigma_z - \epsilon_z$, $\sigma_z - \epsilon_x$ and $\sigma_z - \epsilon_y$) for $\sigma_y = \sigma_x = 0$ for a multi-directional laminate made of carbon/epoxy materials.

Experimental results for the laminate in Test Case 12 were obtained from three different specimens (a cubic specimen, hollow cylinder specimen and waisted (RARDE) specimen). The results show that the specimen's shape and its dimensions have a marked effect on the response of the material. The results from the waisted specimens were used for the benchmark study, as the cubic and hollow cylinder specimens exhibited an apparent premature failure.

Comparison with test data for Test Case 12:

The predicted curves, reported in Ref[34], exhibited a number of contradicting features (degree of nonlinearity, discontinuity) as well as a wide range of values for the strength and ultimate failure strain. Some of the theories predicted linear stress strain curves (e.g. Hansen) and other predicted nonlinear softening behaviour (e.g. Puck, Wolfe, Cuntze-A) while other predicted nonlinear stiffening behaviour (e.g. Pinho, Cuntze-B and Hashin-B). The discontinuities in the curves predicted by Rotem and Tsai-Ha-B are caused by the post failure analysis implemented in the methods.

It should be noted here that the nonlinear stiffening behaviour in the models used by Cuntze-B and Hashin-B was based merely a curve fitting rather than a sound physical basis.

In order to quantitatively assess the correlation between the predictions and the experiments, the ratio (CR) between the measured data and the predicted data was computed for (a) initial Young's modulus, (b) ultimate compressive strength (c) failure strain in the through-thickness direction and

(d) ultimate tensile failure strain in the in-plane direction.

The bar charts in Figures 3 show the values of the computed ratios plotted against the theory designation (name of theory). The same computed ratios are also listed in Table 3 where a colour code is used. The colour code is as follows:

- Green represents a ratio (CR) between 0.9 to 1.1.
- Yellow for a CR between 0.5-0.9 and 1.1 to 1.5.
- Red for CR smaller than 0.5 and larger than 1.5.

The green colour indicates good correlation between theory and experiments while red colour indicates a large discrepancy between the theory and the experiments.

The results show a number of striking similarities and differences and these are listed below:

-9 out of the 12 theories were modified in 'Part B', i.e. upon making the experimental data available. Only Bogetti, Puck and Hansen theories were unmodified.

-Three theories (Carrere, Cuntze and Hashin) made a substantial amount of revision to the results presented in 'Part A'. As a result, the predictions made in 'Part B' were much closer to the experimental results. This can be seen by comparing the colours of these models in Tables 3 (i) and Table 3 (ii).

-The CR for the initial modulus ranged from 0.72 to 1.06 (CoV=10%) in 'Part A' and from 0.82 to 1.13 (CoV=10%) in 'Part B'.

-The CR for the stress at 3% strain ranged from 0.34 to 0.78 (CoV=22%) in 'Part A' and from 0.55 to 1 (CoV=18%) in 'Part B'.

-The CR for the failure stress ranged from 0.18 (Bogetti) to 3 (Hansen) (CoV=131%) in 'Part A' and from 0.18 (Bogetti) to 3 (Hansen) (CoV=100%) in 'Part B'.

-The CR for the compressive failure strain ranged from 0.2 (Bogetti) to 2.8(Hansen) (CoV=102%) in 'Part A' and from 0.2 (Bogetti) to 2.8 (Hansen) (CoV=81%) in 'Part B'.

-The CR for the tensile failure strain ranged from 0.22 (Cuntze) to 1.63(Rotem) (CoV=66%) in 'Part A' and from 0.18 (Tsai-Ha) to 2.54 (Rotem) (CoV=81%) in 'Part B'.

-The CR for the Poisson's ratio ranged from 0.47 (Bogetti) to 5.9 (Hansen) (CoV=103%) in 'Part A' and from 0.47 (Bogetti) to 5.9 (Hansen) (CoV=99%) in 'Part B'.

It can be concluded that the predictions of the behaviour of the laminate in Test Case 12 are very diverse and hence there is no clear consensus on how to predict the strength and deformation under through-thickness compression.

5. Conclusions

The readers are directed to the extensive analysis made in [34] to gain a full appreciation of the status of the maturity of current 3-D failure theories. There were numerous lessons and some of the lessons are listed below:

1- One of the major philosophical points to emerge from WWFE-II is the diversity exhibited between the theories as to whether certain failure envelopes are 'open' or 'closed'. For instance theories of Puck, Pinho, Hashin, Carrere and Cuntze predicted open envelopes (i.e. no failure) under combined transverse and through-thickness compressive stresses of a UD lamina and also open envelopes for a unidirectional lamina and multi-directional laminates under hydrostatic pressure.

2- There was further lack of consensus on whether an isotropic polymeric matrix material (Test Case 1) should be weaker than a unidirectional lamina made of glass/epoxy or carbon/epoxy materials under hydrostatic loading. However, there was insufficient experimental data available to provide definitive answers on these key points – This remains a critical philosophical challenge to future researchers in this field !

3- The predictions of the behaviour of the laminate used in Test Case 12 have exhibited a wide range of diversity. Differences between the theories themselves were large where the ratio between the highest predicted strength (and strain) and lowest predicted strength (and strain) was more than 10.

4- Generally, generating reliable experimental results under 3-D states of stress was and remains a challenging task.

5- In a nut-shell, triaxial failure models are still largely empirical and do require further development and refinement in order to increase their fidelity and accuracy and the confidence for use in design applications. However, the WWFE-II has identified

strong features in each of the models used and the level of accuracy which can be achieved.

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(a)- A schematic of the loading pattern for Test Case 1

(b) Failure Envelope for Test Case 1

(c) A Bar Chart for Test Case 1

Figure 1 A comparison between the theoretical predictions obtained from different contributors and test results for Test Case 1. (a) A schematic. (b) Failure envelope for 'Part A'. (c) Ratio of predicted to measured strength for 'Part B' theories.

(a)- A schematic of the loading pattern for Test Case 5

(b) Failure Envelope for Test Case 5

(c) A Bar Chart for Test Case 5

Figure 2 A comparison between the theoretical predictions obtained from different contributors and test results for Test Case 5. (a): A schematic. (b): Failure envelope for ‘Part A’. (c): Ratio of predicted to measured strength for ‘Part B’ theories.

Table 1 Details of the laminates and loading (test) cases. (Bold text is for the Cases described here in this paper)

Test Case	Laminate lay-up	Material	Required Prediction
1	Polymer	MY750 epoxy	σ_x versus σ_z (with $\sigma_y = \sigma_z$) envelope
2	0°	T300/PR319	τ_{12} versus σ_2 (with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3$) envelope
3	0°	T300/PR319	γ_{12} versus σ_2 (with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3$) envelope
4 ^(a)	0°	T300/PR319	Shear stress strain curves (τ_{12} - γ_{12}) (for $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -600$ MPa)
5	90°	E-glass/MY750	σ_2 versus σ_3 (with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_3$) envelope
6	0°	S-glass/epoxy	σ_1 versus σ_3 (with $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3$) envelope
7	0°	AS carbon/epoxy	σ_1 versus σ_3 (with $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3$) envelope
8	±35°	E-glass/MY750	σ_y versus σ_z (with $\sigma_x = \sigma_z$) envelope
9 ^(b)	±35°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves (σ_y - ϵ_x and σ_y - ϵ_y) at $\sigma_z = \sigma_x = -100$ MPa
10	(0°/90°/±45°) _s	IM7/8551-7	τ_{yz} versus σ_z (with $\sigma_y = \sigma_x = 0$) envelope
11	(0°/90°) _s	IM7/8551-7	τ_{yz} versus σ_z (with $\sigma_y = \sigma_x = 0$) envelope
12(c)	(0°/90°)_s	IM7/8551-7	Stress-strain curves (σ_z -ϵ_z, σ_z -ϵ_x and σ_z -ϵ_y) for $\sigma_y = \sigma_x = 0$

(a)-Please first apply $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -600$ MPa to the lamina. Then apply the shear loading till final failure takes place.

(b)-Please first apply $\sigma_y = \sigma_z = \sigma_x = -100$ MPa and record the resulting strain values. Then increase the stress σ_y (beyond -100MPa) gradually till final failure takes place. Please plot the full stress-strain curves (σ_y - ϵ_x and σ_y - ϵ_y).

(c)- The lay-up used to obtain experimental data was a quasi-isotropic ((-45°/45°/90°/0°)_s) laminate.

Table 2 Details of the participants' names, their organisations and the approaches represented in WWFE-II.

I.D. No.	Participants' Names	Organisation	Approach represented	Theory designation
1	Bogetti, Staniszewski, Burns, Hoppel, Gillespie, [13][28].	U.S. Army Research Laboratory (USA)	3-D Maximum strain theory	Bogetti
2	Carrere, Laurin and Maire, [10][25].	ONERA/DMSC (France)	Micromechanical based Hybrid Mesoscopic (MHM) 3-D approach	Carrere
3	Cuntze, [18][33].	Retired engineer (Germany)	Failure Mode Concept (FMC)	Cuntze
4	Huang, Jin and Ha, [12][27].	Hanyang University (S Korea)	MicroMechanics of Failure (MMF) model	Tsai-Ha
5	Nelson, Hansen and Mayes, [14][29].	Firehole Technologies, Wyoming University, Alfred University (USA)	Multi-continuum micro-mechanics theory (MCT)	Hansen
6	Zhou and Huang, [8][23].	Tongji University (China)	Anisotropic plasticity and generalised max stress	Huang
7	Kress, [17][32].	ETZ Zurich (Switzerland)	Hashin's model	Hashin
8	Pinho, Darvizeh, Robinson, Schuecker, Camanho, [7][22].	Imperial College (UK), University of Porto (Portugal)	3-D physically-based constitutive model	Pinho
9	Deuschle and Kroplin, and Puck* and Deuschle, [15][30].	Stuttgart University, *retired engineer (Germany)	Physically based 3-D phenomenological model	Puck

10	Rotem, [9][24].	Technion University (Israel)	Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory	Rotem
11	Zand, Wolfe, Butalia and Schoeppner, [16][31].	Ohio State University, AFRL, Wright-Patterson, AFB, Ohio (USA)	Modified maximum strain energy method	Wolfe
12	Ye and Zhang, [11][26].	Lancaster University, Manchester University (UK)	Christensen's theory	Christensen

Table 3 A summary of ratios (CR) between predicted and measured data for Test Case 12. Both 'Part A' and 'Part B' theories are shown. The green colour is for ratios between 0.9 and 1.1, the yellow for 0.5-0.9 and 1.1-1.5 and red for ratios less than 0.5 or above 1.5.

(i) 'Part A' theories

	Bogetti	Carrere	Cuntze	Tsai-Ha	Hansen	Huang	Hashin	Pinho	Puck	Rotem	Wolfe	Christensen
Failure strain ϵ_x	(*)	0.66	0.22	0.27	0.48	0.53	0.52	1.03	0.40	1.63	0.33	0.59
Failure strain ϵ_z	(*)	0.52	0.53	0.23	2.86	0.55	0.63	0.56	0.38	1.78	0.54	0.34
Poisson's ratio	(*)	0.78	2.41	0.86	5.92	1.04	1.20	0.54	0.95	1.09	1.65	0.58
Strength	(*)	0.35	0.45	0.29	3.00	0.51	0.44	0.36	0.34	0.30	0.48	0.30
Initial modulus	(*)	1.06	0.89	0.81	0.85	0.95	0.87	0.89	0.96	0.76	0.72	0.87
Stress at 3% ϵ	(*)	0.78	0.69	0.64	0.72	0.75	0.34	0.78	0.75	0.41	0.68	0.73
Secant modulus	(*)	0.45	0.19	0.33	0.51	0.49	0.36	0.67	0.35	0.27	0.29	0.52

(*) means not provided

(ii) 'Part B' theories

	Bogetti-B	Carrere-B	Cuntze-B	Tsai-Ha-B	Huang-B	Hashin-B	Pinho-B	Rotem-B	Wolfe-B	Christensen-B
Failure strain ϵ_x	0.43	0.91	1.14	0.18	0.58	1.12	0.55	2.54	0.40	0.59
Failure strain ϵ_z	0.20	0.80	1.32	0.64	0.38	1.14	0.49	2.10	0.46	0.96
Poisson's ratio	0.47	0.87	1.16	3.60	0.64	1.01	0.89	0.83	1.15	1.64
Strength	0.18	0.57	1.44	0.64	0.35	1.01	0.97	0.41	0.40	0.85
Initial modulus	0.95	1.13	0.89	0.81	0.93	0.87	0.89	0.82	0.85	0.87
Stress at 3% ϵ	0.55	0.94	1.00	0.64	0.81	0.96	0.68	0.69	0.69	0.73
Secant modulus	0.38	0.65	1.24	0.18	0.55	0.99	1.08	0.49	0.35	0.52